

Binuclear Copper(II) Complexes with the Schiff Base derived from Furan-2-aldehyde and Dapsone

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Binuclear Cu^{II} complexes of M₂L₂X₄ type, where L=4,4'-di(furan-2-formylimino)diphenyl sulphone (FD); X=Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and CH₃COO⁻, having octahedral environment around metal ions, are reported. Characterisation of the complexes has been done on the basis of elemental analysis, conductivity, magnetic, ir, uv and esr spectral measurements.

Dapsone (4,4'-diaminodiphenyl sulphone) is one of the most widely used drug for the treatment of leprosy¹. Antibacterial activity in the furan derivatives, containing azomethine group, is also well established². Furthermore, coordination of biologically active ligands with metals often results into the formation of compounds of enhanced activity³. In Indian Ayurvedic system copper has been described to possess strong antileprotic activity⁴ and its compounds are frequently used in pharmaceutical preparations for the treatment of various skin diseases including psoriasis and leprosy⁵. It was therefore, desirable to prepare the Schiff base of dapsone with furan-2-aldehyde and to study its coordination with copper ions.

In the present communication we report the preparation and characterisation of above Schiff base and its complexes with the chloride, nitrate and acetate of divalent copper.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are stable in air, and soluble in DMF, DMSO and THF. Molar conductivity data (Table 1) indicate their non-electrolytic nature. Qualitative tests for anions in aqueous and ethanolic mediums do not give positive results. Elemental analysis and molecular weight data suggest Cu₂L₂X₄ stoichiometry for the complexes, where

X=Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and CH₃COO⁻ and L=Schiff base, 4,4'-di(furan-2-formylimino)diphenylsulphone (FD).

Ir spectra :

In ligand FD, stretching vibrations corresponding to the furan ring oxygen⁶ have been observed as sharp bands at 1 090 and 1 240 cm⁻¹. Sharp bands at 1 125 and 1 290 cm⁻¹ assignable, respectively, to ν_{as} and ν_s sulphone vibrations⁷ of dapsone are observed at the same frequency in the ligand also, with a slight decrease in their intensity (~10%). Appearance of these bands in the ligand molecule indicates that these groups, of respective aldehyde and amine, have not been effected during the condensation. Change in the intensity of sulphone bands may be as a result of the polarising effect of the aldehyde, condensing at both the ends of dapsone, which might have effected the S-O bond character, thus, resulting into a slight change in the band intensity of sulphone group upon condensation.

The ν_{as} (NH₂) and ν_s (NH₂) vibrations of dapsone were found to be absent in FD and a new band in the later has been observed at ~1 600 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the azomethine group⁸, thus confirming the condensation of furan-2-aldehyde with dapsone.

On comparing ir spectra of the complexes with that of the ligand, stretching bands corresponding to the azomethine group and furan ring-oxygen were found invariably shifted 40-60 cm⁻¹ towards

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. conductivity Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ _{eff} B.M.	ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)	
	N	S	M	Cl			Azomethine C=N	furan ring oxygen
Ligand	7.06 (6.92)	7.90 (7.92)	—	—	2.6	—	1 600	1 090 1 290
Cu ₂ L ₂ Cl ₄	5.21 (5.19)	5.92 (5.94)	11.75 (11.79)	13.18 (13.15)	5.2	1.20	1 540	1 030 1 190
Cu ₂ L ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	9.50 (9.46)	5.44 (5.41)	10.59 (10.73)	—	5.8	1.18	1 550	1 040 1 200
Cu ₂ L ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₄	4.99 (4.77)	5.31 (5.47)	10.62 (10.84)	—	5.0	1.21	1 555	1 040 1 190

*L=Ligand (FD)

negative side indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen⁹ and furan oxygen¹⁰ with the metal ions. Strong bands at 620 and 600 cm^{-1} which are assigned as furan ring deformation modes¹¹, also suffered 15–25 cm^{-1} red-shift on complexation, thus indicating the metal-ligand bonding through the furan ring oxygen¹². Considerable negative shifts, as observed in these complexes, indicate the transfer of electron density to a significant extent¹³. This fact also gets support from ν_2/ν_1 values as calculated from the electronic transitions, which are informative about a considerable metal-ligand overlap in the reported complexes.

Sulphone group stretching bands did not show any appreciable shift on either side, which is an indication of non-participation of sulphone group in coordination. Interestingly, the intensity of these stretching bands, was found to be decreased by more than 15% as compared to that of the ligand. This may be attributed as the effect of strong electronic repulsion imposed by the coordinating uninegative anions on the non-coordinating sulphone group of the ligand. Presence of two coordinating nuclei in the vicinity of sulphone groups increases strain on the S–O bonds due to high electronic repulsion of the coordinating anions, which results into a change in the electron density at sulphone-oxygen, thus decreasing the band intensity. In the acetato complex, however, decrease in the intensity of this band is less than 10%, which might be due to a weak electronic repulsion imposed by the comparatively less electronegative acetate ions. Effect of steric repulsion also results into a distortion in the symmetry of the complex molecule. Obviously, the B -values for the complexes, as calculated from the electronic transitions, are strongly indicative of the distortion from the ideal geometry. Hence, the change in the intensity of sulphone stretching vibrations in the ir spectra of the complex molecules may also be assumed as an indication of the distortion from the ideal geometry.

In the chloro complex, medium intensity bands corresponding to the metal-ligand coordination have been observed in the far-ir region at 520, 360 and 280 cm^{-1} which are assignable to M–O, M–N and M–Cl stretching vibrations respectively¹⁴. In the nitrate complex, three additional sharp bands are observed at 1 010, 1 265 and 1 430 cm^{-1} , corresponding to ν_2 , ν_1 and ν_4 modes of coordinating nitrate ion. Since the magnitude of separation between ν_4 and ν_1 bands is 165 cm^{-1} , therefore, coordination of nitrate ion in a unidentate manner is confirmed¹⁵. Medium intensity bands at 530, 450 and 380 cm^{-1} , in these complexes are assignable to M–O, M–N (nitrate) and M–N (azomethine) stretching vibrations¹⁶ respectively.

In the acetato complex, bands at 1 480 and 1 360 cm^{-1} , which are assignable respectively, to ν_{as} and ν_s carboxylic modes¹⁷ of the acetate ion, have been found to be shifted on the opposite sides upon complex formation. This larger separation between the ν_{as} and ν_s frequencies, confirms the coordination

of acetate as a unidentate anion through the C–O moiety of the carboxylic group¹⁸. Metal-ligand bonding vibrations in this complex have also been observed in the expected range.

Electronic spectra: Only one broad asymmetric band observed at $\sim 13\,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the chloro and nitrate complexes and at $13\,600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in acetato complex, is assignable to the ${}^1T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g$ transition. This suggests a tetragonally distorted (D_h) symmetry for these complexes¹⁹.

Magnetic properties: The μ_{eff} values in these complexes, were found in the range 1.18–1.12 B.M. An approximate demarcation given by Figgis²⁰ is that, μ_{eff} values above 1.90 B.M. indicate tetrahedral and below 1.90 B.M. a square-planer or octahedral geometry. However, normally the range for all the copper complexes is 1.5–2.6 B.M.²¹. The abnormal values in the present complexes may be attributed as due to the appreciable magnetic interaction between the two copper ions present in the reported binuclear complexes. Occurrence of magnetic interaction in such cases may also be viewed through either the overlap of Cu–Cu orbitals or through the ligand participation²²; the cryomagnetic and X-ray structural studies may clarify the position more precisely. However, similar type of binuclear Cu^{II} complexes with subnormal magnetic moments have been reported earlier by the other workers²³.

In esr spectra (CDCl_3 , room temperature), X-bands of complexes are indicative of tetragonal symmetry around the Cu^{II} ions in a unit cell with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state²⁴. G -values for the chloro and nitrate complexes (2.76 and 2.77 respectively) and the corresponding g -values indicate the presence of more than one magnetically nonequivalent molecules in a unit cell with exchange interaction between the Cu^{II} ions, thus indicating the presence of two species with an axial symmetry²⁵.

Experimental

Dapson (Sigma) was used as such. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. C and H analyses were obtained from the Microanalytical Division, C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Metal contents were estimated by complexometric titrations²⁶. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldhal's method, halogen by Volhard's method and sulphur by BaSO_4 precipitation method²⁷. Molecular weight was determined by Rast's camphor method.

Molar conductivity (0.001 M solutions in nitrobenzene) was measured on a Systronix 321 conductivity bridge and magnetic moment on Gouy's balance. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a CZ-Specord UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

Preparation of ligand: A mixture of dapson (0.05 mol) and furan-2-aldehyde (0.1 mol) in absolute ethanol (150 ml) was refluxed for 6 h using CaCl_2 guard tube. Ethanol (95–100 ml) was then distilled

off and the solution cooled in freezing mixture for 2 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from absolute ethanol and dried at 84–85°, (13.8 g), m.p. 168°.

Preparation of complexes : A mixture of saturated ethanolic solutions of the ligand (0.005 mol) and the respective metal salts (0.02 mol) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixtures was then cooled in ice for 3 h. The resulting solids were washed with ice-cold ethanol and dried at 84–85°, (60 - 62%).

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